

TRAIN4EU

Transforming ReseArch & INnovation
agendas and support in 4EU+

H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020

Project no.: **101016674**

Start date of project: **1 January 2021**

Duration of project: **36 months**

Deliverable

Reference number and title:

D7.7 – Policy Brief 2

Name of lead beneficiary:

University of Copenhagen

Due date:

31. December 2023

Submission date:

21. December 2023

Dissemination level: Public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674.

ERA POLICY BRIEF

CALL: Horizon2020 - Science with and for Society (SwafS) - Other Actions 31 and 32

TOPIC: "Support for the European Universities on the Research and Innovation dimension"

PROJECT: Transforming ReseArch & INnovation agendas and support in 4eu+ (TRAIN4EU).

Website: [TRAIN4EU+ \(4euplus.eu\)](https://TRAIN4EU+ (4euplus.eu))

FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS (MAX 2 P)

1. Please describe the **challenges** your Alliance encountered in Reporting Period 2 regarding cooperation between universities in the field of R&I in relation to the institutional change areas (transformation modules) foreseen as well regulatory obstacles hampering the cooperation.

4eu+ challenges in fostering cooperation between universities within R&I support domains primarily revolved around the institutional transformation modules. There were internal challenges such as financial constraints as well as external challenges such as regulatory obstacles. A significant challenge was lack of engagement among project members from different universities, in large part due to their heavy overload with other institutional tasks and commitments. Specific challenges in WP1-5 included:

WP 1 Developing common research agenda: Substantial variation in organisational configurations among partners, particularly for research services, continues to be a challenge to coordination and capacity for action across 4eu+. A WP1 pilot action in M23 (see D1.3) confirmed the uneven capacity of enhancing participation, linked to different levels of centralisation/decentralization.

WP 2 Strengthening R&I human capital: Human Resources (HR) became an unexpected bottleneck. Given the unique nature of HR in academic institutions, there were many hurdles, as described in D2.1-2.3 (M6-M35), which the short project time of three years did not allow us to address.

WP 3 Sharing research infrastructure: Great variation in management, acquisition and funding practices continue to pose the main obstacles to sharing research infrastructure facilities within and across universities. Staff challenges in terms of long-term employment of scientific technical experts as well as sustainable and stable models of financing pose the biggest challenges to the recognition and establishment of research infrastructure and Core Facilities networks of European Universities.

WP 4 Linking citizens-academia-businesses: Identifying possible points of connection beyond local and national contexts was a challenge which was not fully met during the project lifetime.

WP 5 Mainstreaming Open Science: Challenges included diverse levels of advancement in OS policies and practices, and diverse levels of investment in open science infrastructures and services at partner universities. An in-depth analysis of national and institutional policies sought to identify how national solutions reflect on local (institutional) implementations, e.g., more support and guidance at national level is needed to initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

2. Please describe how you **tackled these challenges**. Based on your project's experience (and if applicable), briefly outline case(s) that you consider as **good practice** and of interest to other universities or to policymakers.

In M19-36, 4eu+ took several strategic measures to not only address the complex challenges within the various R&I support domains and transformation areas, but also to derive actionable insights that might benefit other universities or policymakers. However, while TRAIN4EU has made tangible progress, without significant financial investment, it remains challenging to upscale actions or ensure their long-term sustainability. Encountered challenges were tackled in various ways within WP1-5, including:

WP 1: The 2021 creation of a 4eu+ legal entity and the consolidation of a General Secretariat enhanced our ability to work towards *a common research agenda* and take actions to enhance bottom-up involvement of researchers' community; this was supported by the launch of internally funded Calls (4EU+ Visiting Prof. & SEED4EU+). Focus was also on enlarging the network of research managers within partner universities to embed R&I activities; incl. the launch of GSS – Grant Support Service.

WP 2: To address project member overload, a flexible approach to workload distribution was adopted. An open channel for sharing best practices, resources, and insights was created, and this cross-pollination allowed universities to benefit from each other's strengths. Despite the hurdles, commitment to the project's vision led to the identification of several potential pilot actions.

WP 3: Excellent practices for mapping, managing and maintaining research infrastructure was developed. To highlight the results and address challenges a paper currently under review in the Journal of Education Policy (see D3.3 & D7.5) was written jointly. Sustainable and efficient research infrastructure facility network on European level, and a funding mechanism for HEI that creates an incentive for universities to invest in an interconnected system of research infrastructures, continues to be called for.

WP 4: TRINEU is developing a "network of experts" around the issues of valorisation and transfer. The aim of this network is to provide an answer to the issues raised and identified as being possible points of connection beyond the local and national contexts. It will do so by facilitating the exchange of good practice with dedicated people on different challenges, including SSH Transfer and relation with SME's. Regular events of this network are organised.

WP 5: Citizen science best practices were investigated, creating the basis for generating recommendations for enhancing citizen science projects and elaborating an interview guide to help partners tackle citizen science. A bibliometric analysis of open access publications within the Alliance was also carried out. Collectively, the infrastructure provided, the legal and journal selection support, and the provision of APC/BPC funding have translated into an increase in open publishing at leading universities.

3. Please describe the **tangible progress** that individual partners as well as the Alliance as a whole have made in terms of introducing changes in their entities as a result of this project.

TRAIN4EU has made progress in terms of facilitating tangible changes in operational aspects and in privileged access to partner universities, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of each institution's inner workings, best practices and challenges. Regular meetings ensure open lines of communication, alignment and progress tracking. Trust between and knowledge about partners may be one of the most valuable progressions coming out of TRAIN4EU. Examples of progress include:

WP 1: WP1 is feeding into the strategic work on the 4eu+ 2025-2035 strategy which includes the R&I dimension. At the level of individual partners, Grant Offices are increasingly working in synergy with the continuous exchange of best practices serving as basis for institutional capacity-building.

WP 2: Significant achievements include scaling up staff exchanges between 4eu+ universities fostering collaborative environments, exposure to various promotion programs as well as adoption of a Performance and Development Review scheme for doctoral candidates by some partners, ensuring guidance, feedback and support. A robust dataset on key areas of concern was gathered, including staff wellbeing, recruitment processes, and gender equality, which can guide future decisions and policies.

WP 3: Tangible progress such as introducing models of centralised management of Core Facilities at our partner universities can only be achieved with a more comprehensive sharing of know-how at university management level. For staff development, a European certificate and training programme for scientific managers with a clear career path could address the challenge of staff brain-drain from academia towards industry. The SwafS project and funding period is too short to achieve this.

WP 5: Re. citizen science, recommendations that may contribute to developing a strategy towards infrastructure and support models was elaborated. Re. research data management, job profiles for new data roles at universities and defined the required skills and competencies for RDM professionals was described. Re. open access publishing, two scenarios of lessons on OA publishing were elaborated. A Toolkit for Open Science Advocacy, e.g., training sessions on open data support, was prepared.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS (MAX 2 P)

1. ... Please provide arguments and concrete examples how your Alliance provides ... added value as compared to 'traditional' cross-border cooperation between researchers, such as through competitive collaborative research projects by the Framework Programme.

Alliances provide universities with a unique opportunity to set up stable R&I collaborations within increasingly integrated contexts, potentially raising excellence and fostering researchers and staff mobility. This is true also for research-intensive universities like those in 4eu+, with added value being provided by:

- **Stable R&I collaborations, long-term perspective across universities' missions:**

4eu+ has created four Flagships as thematic areas that form the basis for multi- and interdisciplinary cooperation in R&I, education and service to society between the current eight member universities. The Flagships focus on issues that play a key role in finding solutions for topical global challenges and initiate and implement a wide range of activities within the Alliance, including joint research projects, joint study programmes, academic conferences, courses for students and doctoral candidates etc. The Flagships allow for teaming up of different and complementary expertise across universities as well as knowledge exchange within the same disciplinary areas thereby raising excellence and attractiveness. They thus provide a stable framework for R&I collaborations that goes beyond the duration of traditional collaborative projects and has the potential of maximizing R&I outputs by fostering in parallel synergies with education and training.

- **Integrated context, common governance and support structures:**

4eu+ was among the very first Alliances to set up a robust governance structure and create a legal entity, allowing for experimentation with internal funding schemes. In April 2023, two 4eu+ Calls, directly funded from 4eu+ universities' budgets, were launched: Visiting Professorships and SEED4eu+. The first fostered mobility of academics across partner universities, while the latter aimed at broadening the engagement of all 4eu+ university communities and at providing seed funding for the implementation of novel ideas within and across education, research, innovation, social outreach and 4eu+ community building. It is noteworthy that in both Calls research was a main driver for participation; in the case of SEED4eu+, the most flagged "project category" which could be chosen was that of research, often combined with education. The outcomes of the Calls and the overall R&I dimension within the Alliance, including TRAIN4EU outcomes, are currently being assessed. The design of future schemes might vary, especially considering the need to strengthen R&I activities vis-à-vis the lack of external funding to anchor outcomes after TRAIN4EU ends.

- **Geographical balance, raising excellence**

4eu+ is composed of leading universities, each in their own national contexts. Whilst similar in terms of profile, partners still exhibit differences, for instance, in terms of capacity to attract EU funding etc. Through long-term and deepened collaboration among equal partners, the Alliance is providing a framework for balancing both institutional capacity building and actual R&I collaborations. Mapping of internal data on the latter (joint proposals, joint projects), also carried out in TRAIN4EU, show initial significant progress.

- **Integrating ecosystems, involving business and external stakeholders**

The creation of a truly integrated European university has the potential to bring substantial added value in the integration of universities' existing ecosystems and in the involvement of external stakeholders within an established and recognizable inter-universities virtual campus. Work on these dimensions is ongoing.

TRAIN4EU activities and learnings have been relevant in highlighting and partially unlocking the above-mentioned added values. Communities of practices have been forming in the fields covered by the project, contributing substantially to the design of shared practices and the setting up of common services in research management, open science, HR, research infrastructures, and transfer to business and society. Yet, the short duration of TRAIN4EU, with only a few implemented pilot actions, did not actually allow for significant changes to be consolidated. The project's outcomes will feed into future strategic steps, with the need to prioritise actions and the risk of putting promising activities on hold due to the lack of follow-up support.

2. The Alliances have repeatedly asked the EU and Member States (MS) to design a holistic support system, covering all their missions at once and reducing administrative burden to a minimum. Please explain your views and suggestions on how this should be realised in practice on the medium and long-term. ... Be as concrete as possible...

4eu+ has joined other Alliances in advocating for the establishment of holistic, long-term funding to deepen transnational cooperation of Alliances across all their missions. A synergies-based approach, indeed, would not only foster efficiency but it would also have relevant multiplying effects in terms of quality and impact. Where only complementarity is feasible, some concrete possible avenues include:

- **Medium-term 2024-2027:** the vast majority of first wave alliances will face a two-year gap with regard to R&I funding. The WIDERA EEI instrument was designed with different aims than those of supporting institutional cooperation among equal partners, proving very problematic for Alliances. If it is replicated it should be at least optimized by reconsidering coordination and budget distribution conditions.
- **Long-term:** funding for R&I should be as integrated as possible with those for education and should include, next to a capacity-building institutional transformation approach, the support of actual R&I activities. Whilst exploring enlarged flexibility in Erasmus+ to encompass some R&I activities (joint trainings, support for early-career researchers, research-based education) could be an option, this would, however, not solve the problem of supporting purely R&I activities (i.e. frameworks for sharing research infrastructures; joint research support etc.). Granting complementary, aligned support for the R&I dimension of Alliances through FP10, especially if linked to ERA policies, can be an alternative/additional avenue fostering the progressive removal of silos across missions. Alliances, indeed, have the potential to substantially contribute to the buildup of the ERA, serving as testbeds for implementation. Competitive funding could cover multiple Actions, providing support for institutional capacity-building as well as include a percentage of the budget devoted to concrete R&I collaborations.
- **Medium and long term:** any measures to favor and align member states' support to Alliances' R&I dimension is also welcome.

Overall, funding opportunities should be aligned and predictable, thus avoiding fragmentation and the risk of spending resources in continuously applying to different Calls and in the management of diverse projects.

3. Please illustrate with concrete examples how your Alliance will integrate the work on the transformation modules developed under this H2020-SwafS support with [Erasmus+ support to the Alliance project](#). Please provide current state-of-affairs and your plans to integrate all missions.

4eu+ is currently developing the Alliance 2025-2035 Strategy which includes Research and Innovation among its four domains. TRAIN4EU outcomes are feeding into the strategic process to explore multiple pathways to link collaboration on research, innovation and societal engagement to the collaborative work already developed in 4eu+ in Erasmus+ funded educational projects. Concrete initiatives include:

- A new joint '**Grant Support Service**' – GSS. The GSS integrates services provided by local grant offices at all universities by acting as a hub for matchmaking for researchers, exchange of information, and assistance to researchers applying for external funding in both education and research. Part of GSS's focus will be on the MSCAs, allowing 4eu+ to link education activities supported by Erasmus+ to research activities. The GSS builds on work carried out in TRAIN4EU WP1, in particular on the RMAs networks, which have broadened and consolidated through joint work.
- There is ongoing work in 4eu+ to develop **Citizen Science**, at the crossroad of education and research. Citizen Science is dealt with in both TRAIN4EU and 1CORE, where front line examples of good practice are drawn upon to develop joint standards and approaches for citizen science activities. Citizen Science in TRAIN4EU is part of WP 5's work on mainstreaming Open Science, also addressed in 1CORE.

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